

Process efficiency and syngas quality from autothermal operation of a 1 MW_{th} chemical looping gasifier with biogenic residues[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Chemical looping gasification is a novel dual fluidized bed technology for the conversion of solid feedstock to a nitrogen-free syngas without the need of pure oxygen. While multiple electrically heated lab-scale experiments have been performed, data on gas quality including tars formed during operation have not been reported yet for autothermal process operation. In this study we present autothermal operation of a chemical looping gasifier with a thermal input in the 1 MW_{th} range, utilizing two circulating fluidized bed reactors with forestry residue and industrial wood pellets as feedstock and Norwegian ilmenite as bed material. A cold gas efficiency of around 50% was achieved in the non optimized pilot plant, indicating that higher values can be reached in a commercial unit when minimizing heat losses. The carbon conversion was around 90%, and this value is expected to increase to almost 100% when raising the temperature, residence time, and cyclone efficiency in a commercial unit. The syngas has a very high quality with methane concentrations in the range of 7 vol.-% to 10 vol.-% and gravimetric tar content below 1 g/Nm³ measured via tar protocol.

1. Introduction

In light of the current climate change, new and renewable sources for hydro-carbons are required. Especially applications where electrification is not an option, such as the maritime transport and aviation sector, and also the production of base chemicals require a constant source of carbon. One such source is biomass, preferably biogenic residues, which can be utilized by gasification. Here oxygen assisted gasification technologies, which produce a nitrogen free syngas, are advantageous as they supply oxygen for heat generation towards the gasifier and no post-gasification separation of N₂ is required. However, for autothermal operation of the gasification process, oxygen needs to be supplied to be able to convert a fraction of the feedstock for the purpose of heat generation, as required by the process. Usually this is done in the form of molecular oxygen provided by an air separation unit (ASU) (e.g. [1]). However, the ASU adds a costly and energy intensive step to the gasification process reducing the efficiency.

One technology avoiding an ASU is dual fluidized bed gasification (DFBG). Endeavours to scale-up the DFBG technology, which supplies only heat and gasification medium but no oxygen to the gasifier, have generated operating experience for approx. 20 yr of demo-plant scale

operation [2,3], producing syngas from biomass with a high amount of tars [2]. However, no large scale (> 20 MW_{th}), commercial DFBG plant is known to the authors, indicating that there are still some technical issues to be resolved. An alternative route is the CLG process which has lately seen increased research activity with multiple review papers being published [4–6]. It combines the idea of supplying heat to the gasifier — like DFBG — with the provision of oxygen by a metal oxide lattice in the circulating bed material, promising to enhance the performance of the DFBG technology.

The CLG process is depicted in Fig. 1 and deploys two reactors, the air reactor (AR) where the metal oxide called OC is oxidized, and the fuel reactor (FR) where the feedstock is converted and the OC is reduced. Both reactors are usually fluidized bed reactors, enabling efficient transport of the solid OC material between the reactors and providing high heating rates and good gas–solid contact for the heterogeneous reactions. Compared to the similar DFBG process, CLG has the advantage of increased char conversion inside the FR, which shifts the generated CO₂ to the FR output. Therefore, almost all produced CO₂ is part of the FR product stream where a CO₂ removal step is already necessary for most use-cases of the produced syngas, allowing for net

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Abbreviations

AR	Air reactor
ASU	Air separation unit
CFB	Circulating fluidized bed
CLC	Chemical looping combustion
CLG	Chemical looping gasification
d.b.	Dry base
DFBG	Dual fluidized bed gasification
FI	Flow indicator
FR	Fuel reactor
GA	Gas analysis
GSB	Gas sample bag
IWP	Industrial wood pellets
KPI	Key performance indicator
LS	Loop seal
OC	Oxygen carrier
OCAC	Oxygen carrier aided combustion
PA	Proximate analysis
PFR	Pine forest residue
PSD	Particle size distribution
SP	Sample point
TAR	Tar measurement
TI	Temperature indicator
UA	Ultimate analysis

Symbols

LHV	Lower heating value (MJ kg^{-1} , MJ mol^{-1})
M	Molar mass, atomic mass (g mol^{-1})
P_{th}	Thermal load (W)
R_{OC}	Oxygen transport capacity
T	Temperature (K, °C)
X_C	Carbon conversion
X_{SG}	Syngas content
Y_{SG}	Syngas yield ($\text{N m}^3/\text{kg}$)
ΔH	Reaction enthalpy (J mol^{-1})
\dot{Q}	Heat flux (W)
\dot{m}	Mass flow (kg s^{-1})
\dot{n}	Molar flow (mol s^{-1})
η_{CG}	Cold gas efficiency
λ	Air to fuel equivalence ratio
c_p	Specific heat ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
w	Mass fraction in solid phase
x	Mole fraction

Subscripts

AR	Air reactor
FM	Fluidization medium Stock
FR	Fuel reactor
FS	Feed stock
OC	Oxygen carrier
O	Oxygen
eff	Effective
in	Stream entering reactor
out	Stream leaving reactor
ox	Oxidized
red	Reduced

negative process chains. Furthermore, the introduction of an active bed material, the OC, adds the possibility of reduced tar generation due to catalytic effects [7–10].

Related research topics range from the experimental investigation of different feedstocks like biogenic residues [11–13] and coal [14] over various bed materials consisting of synthetic oxygen carriers [15], natural minerals [16,17], and waste materials [11]. Moreover, basic de-fluidization phenomena, which can potentially hinder commercial application, resulting from interaction of OC and feedstock ash were studied [18–20], finding no so called “show stoppers”. Additionally to these lab scale investigations, there is activity related to scale-up, with a recent publication on autothermal pilot plant experiments [21] investigating process control concepts relevant for commercial application. Furthermore, simulations are used to optimize process control under autothermal conditions [22,23] and to predict process performance for commercial scale units [24].

So far, no detailed report on generated syngas including higher hydro-carbons from autothermal operation of CLG has been published. However, for large-scale application accurate knowledge of so called tars as well as all permanent gases are vital, as they might restrict use cases or require further processing equipment either for removal or conversion. Furthermore, in contrast to small scale units with external electrical heating, the free variation of process parameters like steam to biomass ratio, air to fuel equivalence ratio, and thermal input to bed inventory is not possible in autothermal operation and the interdependence and restrictions limit the operation range. In this paper we report on syngas compositions, carbon conversion, cold gas efficiencies, and other operation variables obtained from various biogenic feedstocks in the 1 MW_{th} modular pilot plant located at Technische Universität Darmstadt in Germany.

2. Experiment

Fig. 2 shows a simplified flow sheet of the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant used for the experiments. A detailed description is available elsewhere [25]. It depicts the two circulating fluidized bed (CFB) reactors, the cyclones for gas–solid separation, the loop seals and the J-valve for solids transport, as well as the corresponding streams entering and leaving the reactor system. The AR features a height of 8.66 m and an inner diameter of 0.59 m and the FR a height of 11.35 m and an inner diameter of 0.4 m. Measurement sites for the major process streams are indicated, while all other streams entering the reactors are equipped with controlling and measurement devices. The composition of the FR output stream is continuously measured via gas analysis equipment (see Table 1) for the species O₂, CO₂, CO, CH₄, H₂, and H₂O, while the AR output stream is analysed for the components O₂, CO₂, and CO. Additionally the FR output is equipped for tar sampling according to tar protocol/CEN TS 15 439 and for the collection of gas sample bags to obtain data for higher hydro-carbons. The AR fluidization stream is measured for O₂ and CO₂ to determine the oxygen input to the reactor system. Moreover, the AR is equipped with a flue gas recirculation to enable the control of the air to fuel equivalence ratio λ of the process without impacting the hydrodynamics of the AR, as described in [22] and demonstrated by Dieringer et al. [21]. The AR fluidization medium can be electrically heated up to 360 °C and the steam for FR fluidization up to 465 °C.

All OC material discharged from the FR is transported to the AR via a loop seal, while the solids transport from the AR to the FR is controlled via a J-valve. The amount of OC discharged from the AR exceeding the transport between the reactors is returned towards the AR via the loop seal. Both loop seals have sampling ports where solid samples can be obtained and cooled before exposure to the atmosphere to preserve the process oxidation state. From the oxidation state of the solid loop seal samples and the oxygen balance of the AR, the solid circulation is calculated [26]. Both reactors are equipped with an ash sluicing screw to remove bed material and agglomerates, which was used only for the collection of sample material as no agglomeration or meaningful OC deactivation was observed.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the CLG process showing the cyclic reduction and oxidation of an OC material which is oxidized in the air reactor (AR) and reduced in the fuel reactor (FR).

Fig. 2. Schematic of the chemical looping gasification process indicating relevant measurement sites, and sample position. FI: flow indicator, TI: temperature indicator, GA: gas analysis, SP: sample point, GSB: gas sample bag, TAR: tar measurement according to CEN TS 15439.

The option to feed propane to the AR exists to artificially increase system temperature in case of low thermal load P_{th} but was only used for a short time. The produced syngas is cooled and routed to a gas treatment plant for cleaning and sour gas removal to obtain a cleaned syngas useable for the synthesis of liquid hydro-carbons.

2.1. Materials

The feedstocks used for CLG pilot testing are industrial wood pellets (IWP) and pine forest residue (PFR) in pellet form. The industrial wood pellets (IWP) are commercially available wood pellets adhering to the norm EN plus A1. The pine forest residue (PFR) was obtained from foresting operations in Sweden and pelleted by AB Torkapparater. The PFR includes a high amount of bark and pine needles as can be seen in Fig. 3. The properties of the feedstocks are listed in Table 2.

As OC material the natural mineral Norwegian ilmenite was used. Although, thermo-gravimetric analysis show lower reactivity of ilmenite compared to other OC (e.g. nickel based [9,10]) it is still considered a primary option [27] for chemical looping. This is the case, as OC reactivity is not the major concern in CLG where oxygen release by the OC inside the FR has to be actively limited [21–23]. Moreover, it is non-toxic, inexpensive, and commercially availability in the required quantity. In addition operation experience exists for chemical looping combustion (CLC) [28,29]. During experiments, two different Particle size distributions (PSDs), as depicted in Fig. 4, were used. The fine particle fraction has approx. 20% of fines (smaller 50 μm) which cannot be efficiently separated by the existing FR cyclone as shown in previous experiments [28,29] leading to increased make-up rates cooling down the reactor system. In contrast, the coarse material exhibits only 20% of particle smaller 200 μm , leading to lower entrainment from the reactors and thus lower solid circulation [26]. A perfectly matched PSD is

Table 1
Listing of gas analysis equipment for all reactors.

Reactor	Equipment	Measurement principle	Component	Range	Error	Unit
FR	Magnos 206	Paramagnetic	O ₂	0 to 25	0.9	vol.-%
	Caldos 27	Thermal conductivity	H ₂	0 to 40	1.8	vol.-%
	Uras 26	NDIR	CO ₂	0 to 100	3.0	vol.-%
	Uras 26	NDIR	CO	0 to 40	1.2	vol.-%
	Uras 26	NDIR	CH ₄	0 to 20	0.6	vol.-%
	Hygrophil H4320	Psychrometric	H ₂ O	2 to 100	0.3	vol.-%
AR outlet	Magnos 206	Paramagnetic	O ₂	0 to 25	0.9	vol.-%
	Uras 26	NDIR	CO ₂	0 to 30	0.9	vol.-%
	Uras 26	NDIR	CO	0 to 5	0.15	vol.-%
	Hygrophil H4320	Psychrometric	H ₂ O	2 to 100	0.3	vol.-%
AR inlet	Magnos 206	Paramagnetic	O ₂	0 to 25	0.9	vol.-%
	Uras 26	NDIR	CO ₂	0 to 100	3.0	vol.-%

Fig. 3. Raw pine forest residue (PFR) material.

Table 2

Proximate and ultimate analysis of feedstock used during experiments. LHV: lower heating value, PA: proximate analysis, UA: ultimate analysis, d.b.: dry base, IWP: industrial wood pellets, PFR: pine forest residue.

	Component	IWP	PFR
PA [wt.-%]	Moisture	8.3	4.4
	Ash (dry base (d.b.))	0.3	2.3
	Volatiles (d.b.)	84.6	80.3
	Fixed carbon (d.b.)	15.1	17.4
	UA [wt.-%]	C (d.b.)	50.7
	H (d.b.)	6.1	6.1
	N (d.b.)	0.33	0.44
	O (d.b.)	42.5	40.1
	S (d.b.)	0.008	0.025
	Cl (d.b.)	0.008	0.010
LHV [MJkg ⁻¹]		17.2	18.30

not commercially available and sieving proved to be economically infeasible for the pilot tests. The oxygen carrying capacity for the ilmenite was determined to be $R_{OC} = 3.7\%$.

2.2. Operation and balance points

The data was obtained during two test campaigns consisting of more than 14 d of 24 h⁻¹ operation each. The balance points consist of stable operation without operator intervention for approx. 1 h, before a full set of samples — consisting of tar sample, gas sample bag, and loop seal OC material sample — was taken. Gas sample bags are analysed for permanent gases O₂, CO₂, CO, CH₄, N₂, and C₂ to C₃ species. As these

Fig. 4. Particle size distribution of the ilmenite used as oxygen carrier material during experiments.

balance points feature a full set of samples, they are selected for further in-depth analysis.¹

A calculated mean reactor temperature \bar{T} is used during analysis calculated as the mean of all temperature measurements inside the reactor.

$$\bar{T} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N T_i}{N} \quad (1)$$

Although the temperature inside the reactor spans a range of over 100 K and \bar{T} is therefore subject to change with temperature measurement location, it is a useful value for the investigation of the temperature dependency of various parameters. The temperature inside the reactor is a result of feed stock input, OC circulation and amount of fluidization medium supplied to the reactors [22,26]. The main influencing parameter is the solid circulation which can be influenced through adjustments of the J-valve and the system hydrodynamics [21].

For the calculation of the key performance indicators (KPIs), the output gas streams are corrected for the amount of CO₂ input coming from fluidization media i.e. recirculated flue gas in case of the AR and CO₂-fluidization in case of the FR. The loop seal fluidization was switched to N₂ and back to CO₂ for all coupling elements individually to assess the individual impact on each reactor. The input streams were then added during calculation accordingly.

Additional data outside of these balance points is averaged for 20 min and reported here in addition to the balance points to give an indication of further system behaviour. However, transient states —

¹ As this was the first time the plant was operated, the focus was on determining the operation range of the process and plant and not on the optimization of individual operation points. As such, the data set represents a range of possible operation points which are not optimized for cold gas efficiency, carbon conversion, tar generation, or syngas composition.

which are likely to produce large deviations from stable operation because of various system inertias, as have been reported before [21,26] — are included as well.

2.3. Evaluation parameters

The process performance is evaluated using the following parameters:

Cold Gas Efficiency η_{CG}

$$\eta_{CG} = \frac{\dot{n}_{FR,out}(x_{CH_4} \cdot LHV_{CH_4} + x_{CO} \cdot LHV_{CO} + x_{H_2} \cdot LHV_{H_2})}{\dot{m}_{FS} \cdot LHV_{FS}} \quad (2)$$

with x_i being the mole fraction of species i , LHV the lower heating value, and $\dot{n}_{FR,out}$ and \dot{m}_{FS} being the product gas output and the feedstock input, respectively.

Air to Fuel Equivalence Ratio λ^2

$$\lambda = \frac{\dot{m}_{O,AR}}{\dot{m}_{FS} \cdot R_{FS}} \quad (3)$$

with the mass streams \dot{m} and the oxygen requirements for full oxidation R_{FS} . For CLG a slightly modified term for the efficient air to fuel equivalence ratio inside the FR is sometimes more appropriate [21]:

$$\lambda_{FR,eff} = \frac{\dot{m}_{O,FR,out} - \dot{m}_{O,FR,in}}{\dot{m}_{FS} \cdot R_{FS}} \quad (4)$$

The range of $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ in stable operation is between the lower limit of no oxygen release from the bed material $\lambda_{FR,eff} = 0$ like in DFBG, to the upper limit of the oxygen input of the process $\lambda_{FR,eff} = \lambda$.

The **Carbon Conversion** X_C is the fraction of feedstock carbon converted into gaseous species:

$$X_{C,FR} = \frac{\dot{n}_{gas,FR} \cdot (x_{CH_4} + x_{CO} + x_{CO_2}) \cdot M_C - \dot{m}_{CO_2,fluidization} \cdot \frac{M_C}{M_{CO_2}}}{\dot{m}_{FS} \cdot w_{C,FS}} \quad (5)$$

with the AR carbon conversion being calculated from CO_2 only:

$$X_{C,AR} = \frac{\dot{n}_{gas,AR} \cdot x_{CO_2} \cdot M_C - \dot{m}_{CO_2,fluidization} \cdot \frac{M_C}{M_{CO_2}}}{\dot{m}_{FS} \cdot w_{C,FS}} \quad (6)$$

where M denotes the molar mass of the species i and $w_{C,FS}$ the carbon fraction inside the feedstock. Additionally, the **syngas fraction** in the dry product gas is defined as:

$$X_{SG} = \frac{x_{CO} + x_{H_2}}{x_{CH_4} + x_{CO} + x_{H_2} + x_{CO_2} + x_{N_2}} \quad (7)$$

and the syngas yield as:

$$Y_{SG} = \frac{\dot{n}_{gas,FR}(x_{CO} + x_{H_2})}{\dot{m}_{FS}} \quad (8)$$

The **oxidation degree** of the OC material is defined as:

$$X_S = \frac{m_{OC} - m_{OC,red}}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{OC,ox}} \quad (9)$$

In this definition, R_{OC} is the oxygen transport capacity of the OC material, X_S is the oxidation degree of the OC, $m_{OC,red}$ and $m_{OC,ox}$ are the mass of the fully reduced and oxidized state respectively, while the mass of the OC leaving the reactor is m_{OC} .

The sensible **heat transport** \dot{Q} between the reactors can be calculated to:

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{m}_{OC} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T \quad (10)$$

with c_p , the heat capacity of the OC and ΔT , the temperature difference of OC particles at AR and FR output. This neglects heat losses and

² In the case of propane co-firing in the AR, λ is corrected by the mass of propane $\dot{m}_{C_3H_8}$ and the corresponding oxygen demand $R_{C_3H_8}$ ($R_{C_3H_8} = 3.628 \text{ kg kg}^{-1}$).

can therefore be seen as the lower boundary for the sensible heat transported between the reactors. The solid flux between the reactors required for the calculation of the sensible heat transported from AR to FR with the OC material according to Eq. (10) is determined via solid samples and an oxygen balance around the AR [26]. It is assumed, that the heat capacity for ilmenite calculated according to [30] is valid for both oxidation states. The temperature measurements used for calculation are located inside the J-valve and at the top of the FR.

3. Results

The main operation variables for the balance points are given in Table 3. For the first four balance points IWP was used as feedstock, while for the last four balance points PFR was used. For the last point no tar measurement is available.

The temperature profiles in the FR, which are influencing pyrolysis and gasification reactions, are visualized in Fig. 5 with the additional information on fuel input height and OC input height. It can be seen that the reactor is at a constant temperature along almost the full height with only the lower region being much cooler. This is caused by the fluidization medium, which can only be preheated to 465 °C, and the fuel input. From the height where the hot OC from the AR is introduced into the FR upwards, the temperature is at an almost constant level. OC circulation is in the range of 1.8 kg s⁻¹ to 5.7 kg s⁻¹ leading to a feed stock related circulation of 1.2 kg s⁻¹ MW⁻¹ to 4.3 kg s⁻¹ MW⁻¹.

3.1. Syngas production and composition

The dry composition of FR of gases is plotted over FR temperature (a), and $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ (b) in Fig. 6. The high CO_2 concentration is caused by some amount of instrument purge gas inside the FR off gas, loop seal (LS) fluidization medium and by the high energy requirement for the heating of the process streams to reactor temperature. This energy is supplied by Reactions R10 and R9 (details on important reactions are given in Appendix), converting syngas species into CO_2 and H_2O , visible by the increase of the CO_2 content with increasing temperature. The amount of CO_2 coming from purge gases and LS fluidization can be estimated by the difference in CO_2 content of the marked region in Fig. 6 a, where all CO_2 entering the pilot plant was switched to N_2 . The difference is 5 vol.-% to 15 vol.-% in the pilot plant and is expected to be much smaller in large-scale commercial application. This clear trend of increasing CO_2 can also be seen with $\lambda_{FR,eff}$, where higher $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ means higher conversion of syngas species, leading to higher heat release and thus higher system temperatures [21].

For the syngas species CO and H_2 , the opposite trend is visible, low temperatures and $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ correspond with higher volume fraction. In contrast, the methane content shows no change with either temperature or $\lambda_{FR,eff}$, being stable at about 7 vol.-% to 11 vol.-%. This is the same behaviour and range as measured by Condori et al. for a thermal input of 1.5 kW where no dependence of CH_4 to either temperature or λ was observed [17]. Moreover, the range is typical for biomass gasification technologies with steam as gasification agent [2,3,31,32].

The syngas yield per biomass feedstock in Fig. 7 shows the same trends, as the individual species of CO and H_2 , as it is calculated from these species. With increasing temperature and $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ decreases the production of syngas species. The range is with 0.15 N m³/kg to 0.45 N m³/kg lower as for externally heated units (0.34 N m³/kg to 0.89 N m³/kg) [13,17].

The content of syngas species reported here are lower when compared to data reported in literature with corresponding higher amounts of CO_2 . This is not only caused by the reasons stated above (syngas conversion because of autothermal operation, syngas conversion to reach higher temperature, high amount of purges and fluidization for coupling elements) but also by the fact that the values for syngas species reported in literature are normally on a N_2 -free basis (e.g. [11,13,17, 33–35]) while coupling elements are usually fluidized with nitrogen.

Fig. 5. Temperature profiles in the fuel reactor during balance points. Feedstocks: ●— IWP/fine ilmenite, ▲— PFR/coarse ilmenite, ★— PFR/fine ilmenite.

Table 3
Variables of the operating periods used for the investigation in this work.

Description	Variable	Unit	Balancepoint							
			BP_T1	BP_T2	BP_T3	BP_T4	BP_T5	BP_T6	BP_T7	BP_T8
Feedstock	–		IWP	IWP	IWP	IWP	PFR	PFR	PFR	PFR
Bed material PSD	–		Fine	Fine	Fine	Fine	Coarse	Fine	Fine	Fine
Thermal input	P_{th}	MW	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.51	1.56	1.78	1.82
Mass flow of biomass pellets to FR	\dot{m}_{FS}	kg h ⁻¹	230.80	230.80	230.80	230.80	297.30	307.80	350.10	357.20
Mass flow of FR fluidization (H ₂ O)	$\dot{m}_{FM,FR}$	kg h ⁻¹	264.83	213.98	233.02	261.89	299.44	329.68	253.72	230.50
Mass flow of AR fluidization	$\dot{m}_{FM,AR}$	kg h ⁻¹	969.73	972.42	953.47	959.08	1045.20	1100.25	1115.15	1117.41
Mass flow of propane entering AR	$\dot{m}_{C_3H_8,AR}$	kg h ⁻¹	10.04	5.38	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mass flow for LS4.1 fluidization (N ₂)	$\dot{m}_{FM,A.1,N_2}$	kg h ⁻¹	15.62	15.00	16.77	17.40	14.66	16.00	14.18	13.86
CO ₂ flow for LS4.5 fluidization	$\dot{m}_{FM,A.5,CO_2}$	kg h ⁻¹	19.63	14.66	16.66	16.95	0	13.45	13.13	9.11
N ₂ flow for LS4.5 fluidization	$\dot{m}_{FM,A.5,N_2}$	kg h ⁻¹	0	0	0	0	15.09	0	0	0
Flow for J-Valve fluidization (CO ₂)	$\dot{m}_{FM,J-Valve}$	kg h ⁻¹	22.98	11.65	20.21	21.83	18.11	17.86	8.71	8.58
FR pressure drop	Δp_{FR}	mbar	70.68	92.11	125.72	78.79	89.32	61.77	95.25	86.16
Air to fuel equivalence ratio	λ		0.50	0.52	0.49	0.46	0.39	0.38	0.39	0.40
FR efficient air to fuel equivalence ratio	$\lambda_{FR,eff}$		0.35	0.35	0.14	0.13	0.08	0.18	0.15	0.17
Cold gas efficiency	η_{CG}		0.28	0.31	0.27	0.30	0.34	0.38	0.33	0.40
Carbon conversion	$X_{C,FR}$		0.75	0.77	0.59	0.57	0.55	0.66	0.65	0.69
	$X_{C,AR}$		0.11	0.14	0.23	0.28	0.30	0.25	0.18	0.21
Syngas fraction	X_{SG}		0.18	0.22	0.27	0.31	0.40	0.37	0.33	0.39
Syngas yield	Y_{SG}	Nm ³ kg ⁻¹	0.17	0.20	0.21	0.25	0.32	0.34	0.27	0.35
Steam to biomass ratio	S/B	kg kg ⁻¹	1.15	0.93	1.01	1.13	1.01	1.07	0.72	0.65
Mean reactor temperature	\overline{T}_{AR}	°C	933.4	897.6	832.2	808.9	928.2	865.9	915.6	946.3
	\overline{T}_{FR}	°C	840.1	804.1	730.3	716.9	744.2	778.1	827.8	833.7
Oxidation degree	$X_{S,AR}$	%	89.1	82.7	90.7	87.2	99.4	73.6	83.8	75.9
	$X_{S,FR}$	%	61.4	65.0	77.5	76.9	76.9	65.0	68.5	55.6
OC transport between reactors	\dot{m}_{OC}	kg s ⁻¹	2.7	4.2	4.2	4.7	1.8	5.7	5.6	3.8
Heat transport between reactors	\dot{Q}	kW	147.3	270.1	308.8	300.3	263.7	414.9	400.9	363.4
FR syngas flow	$\dot{V}_{FR,SG}$	Nm ³ h ⁻¹	616.6	529.4	506.5	551.2	618.1	696.3	584.1	599.3
	x_{H_2O}	vol. – %	63.7	59.3	61.4	64.3	61.5	59.7	52.2	47.4
	x_{CO}	vol. – % dry	6.7	7.1	9.7	12.6	15.9	13.2	13.1	15.9
	x_{CO_2}	vol. – % dry	69.7	65.4	62.3	58.0	51.1	55.1	59.6	50.4
	x_{O_2}	vol. – % dry	0.2	0	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.1
Gas composition	x_{H_2}	vol. – % dry	10.4	13.8	15.5	16.9	23.6	24.3	20.8	23.7
	x_{CH_4}	vol. – % dry	8.3	9.2	7.2	7.2	9.1	9.0	10.1	10.7
	$m_{tar,grav}$	g N ⁻¹ m ⁻³ dry	0.505	0.124	0.876	2.397	5.156	1.127	1.092	
AR inlet	$x_{CO_2,AR,in}$	vol. – % dry	2.0	2.6	4.2	5.3	4.0	4.7	2.6	2.8
	$x_{O_2,AR,in}$	vol. – % dry	16.9	15.8	14.5	13.8	14.5	14.0	16.0	16.0
	$x_{H_2O,AR,out}$	vol. – %	2.7	1.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
AR outlet	$x_{CO,AR,out}$	ppm dry	2985	1857	262	1370	0	1033	1789	394
	$x_{CO_2,AR,out}$	vol. – % dry	9.7	9.8	12.6	15.0	12.7	14.1	10.6	11.6
	$x_{O_2,AR,out}$	vol. – % dry	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
	$\dot{m}_{AR,out}$	kg h ⁻¹	976	949	994	1017	1138	1188	1161	1159

Fig. 6. Dry gas composition. Feedstocks: \circ — IWP/fine ilmenite, \blacktriangleright — PFR/coarse ilmenite, \star — PFR/fine ilmenite.

Fig. 7. Syngas yield per feedstock mass. \circ — IWP/fine ilmenite, \blacktriangleright — PFR/coarse ilmenite, \star — PFR/fine ilmenite.

Thus, the amount of syngas species is artificiality boosted compared to the ones reported here, where actual process data is reported.³ Therefore, the syngas yield is a more appropriate indicator, as it is independent of the gas species used for fluidization and purging and directly influenced by the feed and performance. The reported values are a bit lower than for externally heated units for the reasons already stated: autothermal operation with comparatively high relative heat losses which are counteracted via higher conversion of the feedstock.

³ N_2 can be considered as an inert and therefore it is reasonable to report N_2 -free syngas compositions. However, the situation is different for CO_2 . As the CO_2 content has an influence on reaction kinetics correcting for the amount of purge gas and fluidization medium would severely reduce the value of the reported data. The main reason to use CO_2 as purge gas and fluidization medium for the coupling elements is to not dilute the syngas with an inert, as it is later cleaned in a gas cleaning pilot plant and subsequently used for liquid fuel synthesis experiments.

3.2. Cold gas efficiency and carbon conversion

The cold gas efficiency η_{CG} and the total (AR and FR combined) carbon conversion X_C of the CLG pilot tests are depicted in Fig. 8 a and b.

The cold gas efficiency is only calculated from online gas analysis as they are the species of interest for further valorization of the product gas stream. As such, higher hydrocarbons (see Section 3.3), which contain an appreciable amount of energy are not included in the calculation. Moreover, the scale of the experiment and the autothermal operation require a significant amount of energy which has to be generated by the conversion of syngas species, resulting in the visible low cold gas efficiencies. In Fig. 8 b two trends C to D and E to F (\rightarrow) for η_{CG} for all operation periods can be observed. They both show the same behaviour at slightly different levels of η_{CG} : with increasing $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ η_{CG} increases, levels off at approx. $\lambda_{FR,eff} = 0.3$, and decreasing again. The initial increase of η_{CG} with $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ is a result of the temperature increase, which in turn leads to higher fraction of fixed

carbon being converted inside the FR. By further increasing $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ the higher conversion of syngas species becomes more important and η_{CG} decreases again. The difference in η_{CG} is caused by the much higher feedstock input for PFR on line C to D compared to IWP on line E to F (see also Table 3). As heat losses are mainly defined by the constant reactor surface an increase in thermal load decreases the relative heat losses and therefore η_{CG} is increased for PFR.

In comparison to literature data on experimentally obtained cold gas efficiency, the values are well below the reported values for very small units (e.g. 1.5 kW [11,17]) and at the lower end of the range reported for small units (20 kW to 50 kW [13]). The range including all operating points (grey markers) indicate that the cold gas efficiency is in the range of other similar sized autothermal gasification plants [32]. Therefore it can be supposed, that η_{CG} will be higher for a large-scale commercial unit than for the pilot plant. In fact, 80% are reported for simulation of a 200 kW unit [24].

It is visible that the carbon conversion exceeds unity for some operating periods which is theoretically impossible for stable operation. However, this is not a problem as long as the average carbon conversion is below unity as during transient operation a carbon inventory can be build up inside the FR or be reduced and converted into gaseous species. In fact, the initial build up of carbon inventory can be seen in Fig. 8 following the path from A to B (\rightarrow). At point A the system was transferred from oxygen carrier aided combustion (OCAC) to chemical looping by switching the FR fluidization from air to steam. The initial drop of carbon conversion can be explained by the slower conversion of the feedstock carbon into detectable gases by steam when compared to air. Therefore, the carbon conversion drops and increases again until a stable carbon inventory inside the FR is reached.

For the balance points where stable operation was targeted, the carbon conversion is always below unity indicating that some amount of unconverted carbon is lost. This loss can happen either through the bottom ash removal or more likely as fines through the FR cyclone. Here the dust passing the cyclone contains about 8 wt.-% to 40 wt.-% of carbon depending on operation condition. The split of the carbon conversion between the reactors is depicted in Fig. 9 a and b and shows a clear trend with FR temperature. The higher the FR temperature, the higher the carbon conversion inside the FR and the lower the carbon conversion inside the AR. Extrapolating the trends observed, the carbon conversion inside the AR — a result of unwanted carbon slip — is expected to reach negligible levels at around 950 °C. For the stable balance points, there is a clear distinction between the utilized feedstocks in the observed carbon slip. The IWP show a higher amount of carbon being converted inside the FR and a lower amount inside the AR when compared to the PFR. This behaviour can be explained by the feedstocks composition (Table 2), where PFR has a higher amount of fixed carbon which needs to be converted either in the FR by gasification through reactions R2 and R1 (see Appendix), or the AR by reaction R14 (see Appendix). As the gasification is kinetically limited, the amount of char inside the feedstock influences the observed carbon slip. For bigger units, i.e. demonstration and commercial scale, an even lower carbon slip is expected, due to a larger reactor size [36]. The higher residence time in larger units allows for more conversion of fixed carbon resulting in lower carbon slip for the same FR temperatures. Therefore, lower CO₂-emissions from the AR are expected in demonstration and commercial plants.

The observed range of $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ is from nearly zero (DFBG-like conditions) to approx. 0.55 and is always below λ . This can be explained by the observed conversion of carbon inside the AR. As some oxygen is used for reaction R14 (see Appendix) not all O₂ is available for the re-oxidation of the OC material through R13 (see Appendix). Consequently the oxygen release inside the FR $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ must be lower than λ if carbon slip is present in a system. Moreover, this explains the observed linear dependency between $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ and $X_{C,AR}$ in Fig. 9 and additionally the fact that higher $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ can correlate with higher η_{CG} in some regions.

When more carbon is converted inside the FR and less in the AR, more syngas can be produced, thus enhancing the cold gas efficiency.

3.3. Production of higher hydrocarbons

The gas analysis equipment in the pilot plant (Table 1) cannot detect species with more than one carbon atom. However, it is known, that a significant amount of feedstock energy is converted into the fraction of hydrocarbons C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, and C₃H₈ during biomass gasification [3,11,17,31]. The production of higher hydrocarbons is analysed for the balance points via gas sample bags and gas chromatography. The production of C₂-species is by far the most dominant not captured by the online gas analysis with a total production of approx. 3 vol.-% and is strongly correlating with the production of CH₄ as depicted in Fig. 10. Moreover, the quantitative value is also in the same range as is reported in literature for C₂-species generated by CLG [13,17,34] and at the lower end of the range reported for DFBG [2]. It can therefore be concluded, that CLG produces syngas with a C₂ and C₃ content slightly lower than DFBG due to the switch to an active bed material.

The production of gravimetric tar as sampled by tar protocol/CEN TS 15439 is visualized in Fig. 11 with additional literature data for steam/O₂ and DFBG as reference. The gravimetric tars give an indication of the generation of species which may cause problems during down-stream utilization of the produced syngas. It is visible, that the amount of gravimetric tars reduces with increasing temperature. There is also a clear difference in the level generated by the different feedstocks, with the PFR pellets producing a higher amount of gravimetric tars than the IWP. However, it is clear from the trend-lines that the gravimetric tars reduce to very low levels for higher operating temperatures. Moreover, the amount of gravimetric tar is below the range reported for steam/oxygen gasification [32] by a factor of 7 to 10 for the same gasification reactor temperature. But even higher tar loads are observed for steam oxygen gasification [31].⁴ DFBG exhibits gravimetric tars in the same range at slightly higher temperatures [37], but values in the same range as measured in the CLG pilot plant are reported for DFBG demonstration plants [38].

The difference between the feedstocks is likely caused by the addition of bark and pine needle in the PFR which is reported to generate a higher amount of tars when compared to wood pellets [3]. The feedstock moisture [38] and the amount of steam available during initial pyrolysis is also reported to have an influence on the generation of gravimetric tars [11,38,39] where lower steam supply or feedstock moisture lead to increased tar formation. This is consistent with the data in Fig. 11, where PFR has lower moisture and produces more gravimetric tars. Considering the higher feedstock moisture and higher gasification temperature reported for DFBG [38] when compared to the data reported here, and the gravimetric tar being in the same region for temperatures from 770 °C upwards, it can be expected that gravimetric tar production is lower for CLG than for DFBG, once again showing the benefit of the active bed material.

The tar species measured via gas chromatography are visualized in Fig. 12 for the balance points. More species were measured but are either not detected or in very low quantities and are therefore not depicted here. There is an appreciable amount of Benzene and Toluene in the produced syngas with some Styrene, Phenol, Benzofuran, and Dibenzofuran. The amount of gas chromatography measured tars is higher than in smaller units with ilmenite [17] by a factor of about 2 to 3. Explanations for this difference include the electrical heating of the smaller units, resulting in a more uniform temperature distribution inside the FR exceeding the temperatures reported here. The autothermal pilot plant has overall lower temperature and a less

⁴ it is not perfectly clear what species are included in "Heavy Tar". As such the gravimetric tar is probably lower and some gas chromatography tars with high dew points are included as well.

Fig. 8. Cold gas efficiency and carbon conversion. Feedstocks: \circ — IWP/fine ilmenite, \blacktriangleright — PFR/coarse ilmenite, \star — PFR/fine ilmenite.

Fig. 9. Carbon Conversion. Feedstocks: \circ — IWP/fine ilmenite, \blacktriangleright — PFR/coarse ilmenite, \star — PFR/fine ilmenite.

uniform temperature profile with much lower temperature at the point of fuel feeding, leading to lower temperatures for initial pyrolysis and char gasification. High temperature is known to be beneficial for low tar production leading to the observed difference. Additionally, the steam content might play a role in tar production [11] but the steam to biomass ratio cannot be freely varied during operation of the autothermal pilot plant due to hydrodynamic constraints [25,40] and are higher 0.65 kg kg^{-1} to 1.15 kg kg^{-1} than reported for smaller units 0.05 kg kg^{-1} to 0.9 kg kg^{-1} (1.5 kW) [17].

Furthermore, the distribution of tars is different than the one reported by Condori et al. [17] for experiments with wood and ilmenite in a 1.5 kW unit, which features high relative amount of Naphthalene and low Benzene. It is more similar to the distribution for ilmenite and wheat straw in a 20 kW unit [13], with high relative amount of Benzene and Toluene. The difference is most likely caused by the lower reactor temperature, especially at the feedstock entry point as lower temperatures favour the production of benzenes over naphthalenes in biomass gasification [41, p. 4f]. However, there might be additional

effects of scale influencing tar generation as the smallest of the units compared here generates a different profile of tars.

Compared to similar sized gasification plants using steam/oxygen gasification [32], higher amounts of Benzene are observed for CLG but lower amounts of Toluene, Phenol, and Indene. However, the total amount of gas chromatography tars is roughly the same. For DFBG plants, the reported gas chromatograph tars reach much higher levels even though gasifier temperatures are higher [2], showing another improvement with the active bed material.

Possibilities in further reducing the amount of tars are the increase of the temperature, the selection of an OC material which results in lower tar production e.g. steel converter slag (LD-slag) [12], or the increase of FR inventory and thus bed pressure drop [38]. The first option is the obvious one, but has the trade-off of lower η_{CG} . The second would require the replacement of the bed material and can therefore not be assessed with the available data, while for the third the data set is too small to show clear trends. Moreover, it is unclear whether effects of bed inventory on tar generation observed by [38] are an effect of

Fig. 10. C_2 -production. Feedstocks: ●— IWP/fine ilmenite, ▲— PFR/coarse ilmenite, ★— PFR/fine ilmenite.

the bed or of feeding location in relation to the bed, which is known to make a difference [37,42]. Nonetheless, the presence of bed material above the feedstock entry point seems to play an important role in tar reduction. When the feedstock is introduced in the lower bed region, the tars generated from initial pyrolysis have a higher residence time in the dense zone of the bed and therefore a higher likelihood of being converted by the bed material.

4. Discussion

Combining the results obtained from the pilot tests of the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant allows to establish various optimization routes and strategies for further development. However, as with all gasification technologies, there exists a trade-off between high carbon conversion and syngas quality (i.e. low tar content) on one side and high cold gas efficiency on the other. The carbon conversion and syngas quality require high temperature, as was shown in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, while the cold gas efficiency is necessarily reduced when operating at higher temperature, as the heat has to be generated from feedstock conversion. However, it was observed that higher temperatures can lead to an increase of the cold gas efficiency, in cases where the benefit from the reduction of the carbon slip from FR towards FR was higher than the required feedstock conversion for the temperature increase.

Effects of the scale of the experiment, where relative heat losses of the reactor system are in the range of 12% to 19% [29,43] for the Balance points, are clearly the low cold gas efficiency and the comparatively low temperature. While optimum FR temperature regarding carbon conversion and gas yield is in the range of 850 °C to 900 °C for the CLG process with Fe based OC [6,34,35,44], this temperature could not be reached during the experiments. However, attaining higher FR temperatures will not pose an issue in commercial CLG units, as relative heat losses are significantly reduced due to the better surface-to-volume ratio. Furthermore, the modular pilot plant has fluidization medium preheating up to 360 °C at the AR and 465 °C at the FR, and the final heating to process temperature occurs inside the reactors. The required energy for the heat up of all process streams to reactor temperature is 18% to 28%. However, higher preheating temperatures are realistically obtainable, especially for the AR, reducing the cooling effect of the fluidization on the reactor temperature and increasing cold gas efficiency [23]. Increasing the fluidization medium temperature at the FR will also increase the temperature of the initial pyrolysis, therefore reducing the tar production. Moreover, char conversion inside the FR will be enhanced with the increase of the bed temperature, resulting in lower carbon slip towards the AR and thus increased syngas

production inside the FR. It can be supposed that the extrapolated FR temperature for very low carbon slip, as indicated in Fig. 9, is actually lower. This will also reduce the difference between λ and $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ as less oxygen is consumed for the conversion of carbon inside the AR. Considering these effects, the heat losses, and the energy requirement for fluidization medium heating, which is combined about 30% to 50%, the 80% cold gas efficiency obtained from simulation for a 200 MW unit [24] seems plausible.

Further optimization regarding the syngas quality are obtainable for green field plants by optimizing the feedstock input location in regards to the bed height and the FR fluidization medium temperature. The longer the residence time of the pyrolysis gases inside the bed, the higher the likelihood of conversion with the OC material. However, placing the feedstock input right at the bottom results in temperatures during initial pyrolysis close to the fluidization medium temperature. The increase of the reactor inventory as much as possible without negatively impacting reactor hydrodynamic is therefore the first option, and can also be varied during operation. The complete replacement of bed inventory with a different OC material to enhance tar conversion is also possible during operation as long as a suitable PSD can be obtained. Here, changes are possible during operation, but require more time than the variation of the reactor inventory. Moreover, selection of bed material should be done to balance multiple requirements [25,45] and not just one parameter.

The presented data exhibits lower temperatures (700 °C to 850 °C) than would be ideal for the process (850 °C to 900 °C) which results in estimations and extrapolations to process temperature, which are not ideal. Moreover, some extrapolations are inevitable, as the modular pilot plant, the size of the experiment, and the autothermal operation lead to comparatively low efficiencies. However, the data gives valuable insight in the operation range and interdependence of process parameters, important trends identified and discussed are still valid. Although quantitative values differ from optimal process range, the results from autothermal pilot testing indicate the technical feasibility and the range of expectable KPIs of industrial scale CLG.

5. Conclusion

Based on the presented results from experimental autothermal operation of CLG in the 1 MW_{th} scale where more than 100 t of biomass have been converted in over 400 h of CLG operation, the following conclusions can be made:

- The possibility of syngas production using autothermal CLG was demonstrated. Although temperatures were about 100 °C below the range for optimal process performance, caused by the scale and autothermal operation.
- The analysis of the syngas generated from biogenic feedstocks showed that CLG produces a high calorific syngas which can be further processed. The amount of CH_4 generated is with 7 vol.-% to 10 vol.-% in the same range as with other biomass gasification technologies.
- The obtained cold gas efficiencies of up to 50% is in the same range as reported for similar sized pilot plants for other gasification technologies. It is expected that the cold gas efficiency reaches up to 80% for commercial CLG units, due to lower relative heat losses and heat integration.
- The observed carbon slip is dependent on the amount of fixed carbon of the feedstock and the FR temperature.
- The amount of higher hydrocarbons is lower than for other gasification technologies. Gravimetric tar productions below 1 g/N m³ make CLG a prime candidate for the syngas production where low tar loads are required. Optimization of reactor temperature and inventory will reduce the amount of tars even further.

Fig. 11. Gravimetric tar on a dry gas basis. Feedstocks: ●— IWP/fine ilmenite, ►— PFR/coarse ilmenite, ★— PFR/fine ilmenite, Barisano et al. [32], Broer et al. (“Heavy Tars”) [31], Kern et al. [37], Kuba et al. [38].

Fig. 12. Tars as measured by gas chromatography for the Balance points.

- The utilization of the active OC as bed material is advantageous compared to inert bed material with higher conversion of C_2 and C_3 species as well as pyrolysis tars.
- Although no optimization of operation was performed, the results are comparable or even better than for other gasification technologies. It is expected, that optimization for either of the KPI will lead to a superior process performance of CLG.

Therefore, CLG can be considered as an option for the sourcing of carbon from biomass for either chemical production or synthetic fuels. Nonetheless, more research is required for optimization of individual KPI. The effects of reactor inventory and feedstock entry location on carbon conversion and tar production need to be quantified to be able to optimize reactor design. Experiments with different OC material could show improvements for individual KPI, especially a lower tar production.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Falko Marx: Conceptualization, Investigation, Data curation, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Paul Dieringer:** Investigation, Data curation, Software, Writing – review & editing. **Jochen Ströhle:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Bernd Epple:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix. Important reactions for the chemical looping gasification process

In order to adequately understand the phenomena described in this study, some underlying fundamental reactions have to be considered. The feedstock conversion process, from solid to syngas, starts with an initial pyrolysis and afterwards the following heterogeneous gas–solid reactions occur during CLG, converting the fixed carbon to the gas phase:

The homogeneous gas phase reactions between pyrolysis gases, converted fixed carbon, and the gasification agent steam are:

with reaction R6 being the combination of the two reactions R5 and R4. As only R3 and R4 are exothermic it becomes clear that the gasification process inside the FR is endothermic. Moreover, the reaction enthalpies of R5 and R6 show that CH₄ decreases with increasing temperature. The heat required for the FR reactions to occur is provided as sensible heat by the OC material to the gasification process and the following heterogeneous gas–OC reactions occurring inside the FR:

The solid–solid reaction R12 between char and OC is less relevant than the gas–OC reactions R7 to R10 as it is slower [46,47] except for very high reaction temperatures [48].

The sensible heat provided to the FR by the solid OC material is generated by the following exothermic reactions inside the AR:

The reaction enthalpy of the heterogeneous gas–solid oxidation reaction is dependent on the used OC. For ilmenite it is actually a combination of the reactions $\text{O}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{TiO}_5 \longrightarrow \text{FeTiO}_3$ and $\text{O}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \longrightarrow \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, with reaction enthalpies being $\Delta H = -454.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta H = -472 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively [27]. Thus, the OC transports sensible heat and oxygen from the AR to the FR and chemical energy from the FR to the AR. R14 is caused by the undesired carbon slip from FR to AR and is favoured above reaction R13. However, in practical operation of CLG, some amount of the carbon slip is not converted inside the AR and transported back towards the FR [26].

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